

yalbompum? yspmta&tomorif

armi hirmi hqC

pmwrft uDf

ppmwrftuul ylorif jylpirtwuf taxmuftujzpap&e&n&G lum a&om;cygon/
 ydwlN bompumr&EG ES h ydtu&m? yspmta&tom;&, lP ajymi fvz&B&krsm;ul
 yk'hcwlv&latmi qupy&azmfym;ygony/ taxmuftxm;rsn;ul Ell f, Dpppbnh
 enf;ul tajcyl&avhvmxm;ygony/ avhvmrit& ydwlonf tqh&AnfoNygaom
 wufusoh g;r&f&h bompum;ul toh jylon/ pmta&tom;ul at' (2-3) &mpceifS
 pwif at' (12)&mpk tapmyh f;umvtxd a&om;cuon/ yk'hcwlv&f jrefmpm
 ta&tom;ES hacwlv&f yspmta&tom;f&h&umi f avhvmaw&f&cygon/
**aontsupum;v&rsn - urh&fpm? acwlv&f pmta&tom? acwlv&f bompum?
 pmta&tom? wufusoh edfrib& Anf, D&b&?
 bompumr&EG ? o&oauw? tu&m? tu&myh
 tajcpm&hi , ? tqh&Anfoh ton&f& pepf**

edgef

a&Sa [mi f&olawoerS taxmuftxm;op&rsn; aw&f&f? , ci&aw&f&xm;aom taxmuft
 txm;rsn;t& jrefm&ajray:w&f jrefm&w&rv&w&f&D aex&h&chom ydvr&f&rsn; f&h&umi f;ul
 chl&monfxuf chl&rmvmapygon/ x<w&lv&h&umi h ydtu&m yspm ta&tom;rsn;ul
 avhvm&if yd, O&ausr&br&f&f azm&xl&v&a&tw&lv&f taxmuftujzpap&ef ppmwrftuul
 jylp&cygon/

ol&woe&n&f; tsuESf&tol&yl&enf

ppmwrftuul ylorif jylpirtwuf taxmuftujzpap&e&n&G lum a&om;cygon/
 taxmuftxm;rsn;ul Ell f, Dpppbnh&enf;ul tajcyl&f? avhvmxm;ly&f? ydwlN
 bompum;r&EG ES h ydtu&m? yspmta&tom;&, lP ajymi fvz&B&krsm;ul yk'hcwlv&
 w&latmi f qupy&azmfym;ygony/

tu&mpmta&tomofyif

, ae jrefm&ajray:w&f ydurh&fpm&rsn;ES h tu&mpmta&tom;rsn;ul yd, O&ausr&
 x&f&um;&ma' orsm;w&f aw&f&ri&ae&ygon/ x&lydurh&fpm&rsn;onf yd, O&ausr&
 y&f&um;ES h ydpmayq&h&om orif taxmuftxm;wp&f&yl&f&cygon/

* a' gu&fvm? w&f&u&fygarmu? jrefmpm&me? yb&f&w&uio&lv/

1/ at'(2)&mpR tEd ajrmuyllftu&mrsmull tajccbf

ylwlonf rdtwlltohlly/aeom ylpum;twluf vlttylvmaom pmta&tom;ull tEd ajrmuyllfa'o pmta&tom;wlls tajcc&, cl[efwygon/ talumi/rh yltu&mwllNoofyiitaetxm;rm;onf ajrmuyllft tEd tu&mwEsha, bk soabm waejci, jzplygon/ (armi hmi hq 2010? 7) atmuygZ, m;(1)ullunlyg/

Z, m(1) jAm[E u&mpwizBzlrESHystu&moifjiEhf, Dfi

tu&mrn		celh&umv	tu&myl
(a&stEd) jAm[P		bpl(3)	
ajrmuyllft	rx&m	at'(2)	အဟုဒေပုဇာပုဗ္ဗ အဟုဒေပုဗ္ဗ
	ube	at'(2)	=၇၅ အဟုဒေပုဗ္ဗ
	*lyA	at'(4)	အိဗဒတိဒိယု မဟုဇဉ်
(a&sjrefm) ysl		at'(3)	
awmi lyllft	tE&	at'(2)	'မဟုဇဒ်ဟုဗ္ဗိယု နာဗ
	arm&d	at'(3)	အံ့ဟုဇာပုဗ္ဗ ဝဟုဇ
	yv0	at'(4)	အိဗဒတိဒိယု မဟုဇဉ်

pZ, m;wllf tEd jAm[E u&mwllawmi lyllftajrmuyllft pwiufym;p0fuyif obmpth jcm;em;aom tu&mrsm;ES hEhf, Dlum azmfyxm;ygony/ (armi hmi hq 2010? 8)

xltjyif Asnf, Df o&a&;om;rl pepfhnvnt, Asnf,tu&mwptclul xu? atmu? O? , m rS Asnf, Df o& oaufrsm;, Dlvh ompeplul tohllykxm;ygony/ (armi hmi hq 2009? 3) Z, m;(2)ullunlyg/

Z, m(2) yslAsnf, Dfb&a&;omrpepf

	t	td	tk	at	atm	th
ysl	—					

azmfyyg taxmuftxm;rm;t& ylwlonf pmta&tom;twwlul a&stEd ajrmuyllfta&tom;ull tajcclum wwajrmucMu [efwygon/

2/ rrbmompumtwuf jylyizelwjcifsm

ajrmuyllitEd ta&tomrsmull tajcck, &mw6? tiflt n&d eftEG f (azarmiwi? 1958? 31-33/) a&stEd pumwEsh jcmemaeaom yswltwuf tu&m ton/\$ pef Transcription ull &, &mw6f rrbpum,oltm; ull pmjyl&ef rsmptcutl c[elwlygon/ (armi&armi&aq6 2010? 9/)

xltwuf rrbpum,obepull ull pmjylEllaom ta&oaulvpeprsm;ull wdk&ctlygon/ xi&haomom'utjzpf tpubaulw tolykri (armi&armi&aq6 2012? 2-11/) Esh tajcpmvli, h&omrsm (armi&armi&aq6 2009? 3/) jzplygon/

2? 1/ tpubaulwtolykri

rrbpum;obepull ull pmjylEllaom ta&oaulv peprsm;ull wdk& &mw6f ysbmom pum;twuf ta&ygaom tohterhtjrihtwuftupeprsm;onfi a&stEd ta&peprsm;rStohtwlt&si azmjaom oaulwv mujzihv&vmurh1/2yg/ rrbmom pum;\ wufusoh (Tone) rsm;ull ull pmjylEllaom tpubaulw peprsm;ull yswltwufctlygon/ atmuygZ, m;(3)ullunlyg/

Z, m(3)o&oaulw wpt&wufi tolyj tpubaulw, 9lwEllaom (armi&armi&aq6 2-11/)

	edjriob(1)	edjriob(2)	edjriob(3)	edjriob(4)	edjriob(5)
	ys-o&oaulw	atmuftpu wpt	, nab;tpu (2)c	, nab;(2)pu atmu(1)pu	, nab;tpu (3)c
t-o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	—	—	—	—	—
t#o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	~	~	~	~	
tk-o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩			
	∩				
at-o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩	∩	∩	
atm- o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩	∩	∩	
	∩	∩	∩	∩	
t#o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	
t#o&oaulw\ edjrioblytpuf oaulvrsm;	∩	∩	∩	∩	

	edfrib(1)	edfrib(2)	edfrib(3)	edfrib(4)	edfrib(5)
	yl-o& oauw	atmutpuf wptk	, mab;tpuf (2)ck	, mab;(2)puf atmu(1)puf	, mab;tpuf (3)ck
edfriblytpuf oauwrs;					
t#o&oauw\ edfriblytpuf oauwrs;	ḿ	ḿ	ḿ		
	ḿ	ḿ			

azmfyygZ, m;t& ylw\bmompum;onf toerrih t&nftaoG ig;rdtxd
 ½Mumif tpubauw ta&pepft& oElygon/ wufuslbmompum; (Tone
 language) toMiykaom vr&jzpbMumif, cilrmpbn azmfyElygon/

2? 2/ tajcpmvNi , h&;omri

rtfpm;oppeful ul fm;jyEhaom ta&;oauwpeprsm;ul wlxGc&mwGf tjcm;
 tEd pmta&;tom;wlvGf raw&aom pmMumiftajcu pmvNi , h&;rsm a&;omrlul
 aw&ygon/ jreEmEli hstapmyllfynm&srsm;u jAm[pmvHrsm; [qMuygon/ xyrSwf
 a&;om;rrsm;ygoi h&ei jAm[pmvHrsm; r[kvlyg/ ydpmvHrsm;omjzplyd t&G ftpm;
 xuDurG , h&mi h&;xm;jcifom jzplygon/ atmuylgZ, m;(4)uMunlyg/

Z, m(4)tajcpmvNi , h&;omxmri

pOf	ausupmtrni	rf&qumv	tu&mylumelwtsuf
1	[elvi foc&fys ausupm	at' (3)	
2	rllfarmjre' ylausupm	at' (3)	
3	oulefyla usupm	at' (4)	
4	ueDu&bcgifiulef?aiGukvf	at' (4)	

pwlvnt pmMumiftajcu&;jci? rlvpmvHxuf xuDurG , jci? rlvpmvH
 E&ctMum; a&;av&jci? tpubauwlygvGf xlbauw atmuwG h&;jci? [hom
 tajctaersm;amumih t-owbabm[hom , lqrrsm;vnt ½Elygon/ o&omf
 xlbauw pmvHrsm;onf rlvtoE&ctS wptcES h&ajyypbn qupyhaom oabmuH
 aw&ygon/ tqMAsntobabm ouDihaonh taetxm;jzplygon/ tqMAsntoh
 ygaom bmompum; [kr&fqElygon/ (armi h&mi h&qG 2009? 13/)

azmfyygoabmt& ydpmwlvf vnf, xlyrsv&om; rism; ygOim? t [lufxlyrsvf [k
 qEh haom xlyrsvrsm; ygOihaygon/ xlyrsvquvuzvmaom Bwfbklyrsvrsm; vnf,
 ygOihaygon/ xlyrsvmifysl pmta&; tom; wof [elvifocsh fpmont t [luf xlyrsvESh
 rOf; wlyrsvf a&maxfygOiharhalmumihaw&orOlysurhifpmsm; wof tapmqh [krsvf, h
 ygon/ atmulygyllunhyg/

y(1) [elvifocsh fpm

xlaemufaw&aom ydpmwlvf t [lufxlyrsvrsm; ubm tohlykalmumif, aw&yg on/ azmfychaom Z, m; (4) rSylrsm; ulunh&avlmEh fyon/

(2) tfo&oauw xlycmrl

ydpm ta&; tom; wof tfo&onlvnf, xlycm; aom ta&; ofyijzplygon/ ydpmwlvf
 tfo&uhtu&mjzih] } a&; om; avhlyb? Asnf, Dfo& oauwul] } } oauw jzih
 a&; avhlygon/ (armi harmi hq 2010? 13/)

ohom&stEd ta&; tom; rsm; wof azmfyavh&om o&shb&oauw tfo& tu&ESh
 tfo&Asnf, Dfo& oauwul hlydpmwlvf tohlykrhaw&yg/ (onjrw? 1958? 4/)

(3) tko&oauw xlycmrl

xltwl tko&a&; om; rES hywbouf vnf, xlycm; rism; aw&yg on/ ydpmwlvf tko&uht
 tu&mjzih] } } a&; om; avhlyb? Asnf, Dfo& oauwul] } } oauw rsm; jzih
 a&; avhlygon/ (armi harmi hq 2006? 15/)

ohomf a&stEd ta&; tom; rsm; wof azmfyavh&om o&shb&oauw tfo&tu&ESh
 ESht-Asnf, Dfo& oauwul hlydpmwlvf tohlykrhaw&yg/ pwofqlvbnf rsh
 o&shb&ESh ta&; pepf rly [qjicif [kwlyg/ , ifo&shb& oauwul a&stEd
 ta&; tom; rsm; ubm -a&; cpep? v&udwifqtwpep? Esh&smifiipeprsm; jzihrohcif
 ubmqhlygon/ Z, m; (3) wof azmfyxm; aompeprsm; ES hwlulqll&avhlymyg/

jAm [dtu& ta&; tom; zlykrl avhlmcsursm; t&vnf ydpm\ uylm; aom ta&;
 ofyifullawqriEh fyon/

Z, m (6) jAm[t u&nESfta&;tom, z&hrylyZ, m

pmv	jAm[P	uk/ef	tEd ajrmuyll f			tEd avmi yll f			yl
	BC-3	AD-2	AD-3	AD-4	AD-7	AD-3	AD-4	AD-5	AD-3
um	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	
ud	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ
ud	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	
uk	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ
ul	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	
au	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ
aum	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ	ƒ

Z, m; t& (t) o&r&ritpubaukvjzplf ajymi f,vh r 1/2 yg/ (tm? at? atm) o&w&r&n vnfr&ofajzmi ES hr&of&h&zplu&v&on&rst y x&jcm; aom ajymi f,vh raw&yg/ o&omf (t& t) ES h (tr t) o&rsm; onf acwftvlu f vub&; p 1/2 u&ajymi f,vh 1/2 yg onf (t& t& tr t) a&; x&rsm; onf ajrmuyll f tu&m? avmi yll f tu&m oabmwlyg O i 1/2 r u acwftvlu f u&v&u&umi f,vnf Z, m; t&jri&aw&E&lygonf/ Z, m;(6) \ aemu f q& aum f v&w&f y&o&oau f w a&; om; r&peprsm; u& azm f y x m; &m tEd ajrmuyll f? avmi yll f ta&; tom; w&ES h u&ym; jcm; em; aom u& yll peprsm; ES tom 1/2 &ech&umi f aw&ri&E&lygonf onf

(4) jAm[t u&r&S at '(2-3) cell of u&vpr&f

yl&w&on&pmta&; tom; u& a&S tEd ta&; tom; r&, &mw&f tu&m w&N taetxm; t& tEd ajrmuyll f a' o pmta&; tom; w&S t&jcc&, b&f ewlygonf/ tal&umi f r&n y&st u&m w&N of yiftaetxm; rsm; onf ajrmuyll f tEd tu&m w&ES ha, b& s oabmw&e&jci f jzplygonf/ Z, m;(1) u&N unlyg/

o&mw&f jAm[t u&m w&N ajrmuyll f to&f u&rsm; ES hvnf xyw&h&r&v&h&r& 1/2 yg/ tu&mt&of rsm; uyif ajrmuyll f tu&mt&of rsm; ES h w&h&r& 1/2 yg/ at' (2) &mpk ajrmuyll f ubeta&; tom; w&ES h tu&my&rsm; cyqiqi 1/2 yg/? Asnf, Dfo& a&; q&f rsm; w&f jcm; em; onf tx&ojzi h Asnf, Dfo&]-] ES h Asnf, Dfo&]-] a&; om; r&rsm; w&f xi&f&n;

azmfyrhsm; onf tu&myht & r&fqrjy/kxm; jci fom jzplygon/ pumv w&f y&spmrsm; u&ll
 a&usupmw&ll frsm; w&ll bmr u ai &xnfy pnf? tkw&csy? w&ll qy/w&ll w&ll w&ll vnf, aw&ll ygonf/
 Z, m; (8) u&ll unfyg/

Z, m(8) y&spmt rsm; q&ll w&ll a&om umv r&f y&spmrsm

pOf	a&usupmtrnf	r&fqumv	tu&myhtumu&ll w&ll csul
1	oa&aw&mf o&ll d O&ll ur r&ll &ll m; t&ll t&ll at mu&ll c&ll su&ll E&ll n y&ll pm	at' (4-5)	
2	oa&acw&mf ci buef? ai &ll kv (at mu&ll ft em;)	at' (5-6)	
3	oa&acw&mf ai &ll yv&ll n? y&ll pm	at' (5-6)	
4	[e&ll v&ll i? O&ll a&ll qmi f, m? y&ll a&ll usupm	at' (5-6)	
5	oa&acw&mf O&ll D&ll m P&ll rmi v&ll n y&ll a&ll usupm	at' (6-7)	
6	o&ll p&ll n&ll r&ll le, ? q&ll i &ll n y&ll a&ll usupm	at' (6-&)	
7	oa&acw&mf ue D&ll u&ll acgi f, ulef? y&ll -ou&ll we&ll b, y&ll pm	at' (6-&)	
8	oa&acw&mf b&ll &ll ma xmi ft&ll t&ll t&ll y&ll pm	at' (6-7)	
9	oa&acw&mf ri w&ll uef y&ll a&ll usupmw&ll f	at' (6-7)	
10	ai &ll t&ll t&ll z&ll	at' (4) a&ll em&ll y&ll ll f	
11	oa&acw&mf ajr w&ll qy/w&ll rsm;?	at' (4) a&ll em&ll y&ll ll f	
12	oa&acw&mf mt kv&ll c&ll pmrsm;?	at' (4) a&ll em&ll y&ll ll f	

azmfyygumvty&ll f&ll tjcm; (at' (4)&mpc&ll l&ll S (at' (7)&mpc&ll e&ll n&ll y&ll acw&ll n&ll pmayta&ll
 tom; trsm; q&ll w&ll a&ll om umv tjzpl r&ll q&ll E&ll ll ygonf/ y&ll spmayz&ll n&ll r&ll umv [k q&ll v&ll y&ll g
 onf

(3) acwlyl bompum? pmt a&t omwESjcmemaejci f

yswlonf rrbompum;twuf yspum wlxicuaomvntf rrbompum;Esh
 acwlyl jzpaom tjc;bompum;rsn;twluul rrt\ ystum? yspmta&pepful
 tolyla&om;rtjylyg/ rrtwvucbom bmojcm;pum;\ rvtum? ta&pep
 twll f &, la&om;avlygon/ Z, m;(9)uunlyg/

Z, m;(9) acwlyl bompum? pmt a&t omwESH Ellf, Sjyxmri

r&f q umv	y t u & myk (y l b m o m t w l u)	*k a' Oem* & D t u & myk (o u w b m o m t w l u)	t E d a w m i y l l t u & m y l r s n; (y g V b m o m t w l u)
at' 0 (2-3)			
	[e v i f ? o c s f y s p m		
at' 0 (3)			
	r l l a r m ? j r e ' y s p m		
at' 0 (3-4)			
	o u l e f ? y s a u s m u p m		
at' 0 (4-5)			
	o a & a c w & m ? b & m ; B u d t 1/2 t ? a t m u c h s u E n ? y s p m		
at' 0 (5-6)			
	o a & a c w & m ? c i b u l e f ? a i l u k w l y s p m /	o a & a c w & m ? j r i f o m [k b & m ; X m y e m v l u ? q i f w l y v i b o u w p m /	o a & a c w & m ? c i b u l e f ? a i l u k w l y g V b m o m /
at' 0 (5-6)			
	[e v i f ? O b a q m i f , m y s p m	& c h l a O o m v b c w l o u w p m	o a & a c w & m ? w l f l y l l r l l a y g u l y g V b m o m /
at' 0 (6-7)			
	o a & a c w & m ? u e D u a c j i f u l e f ? y v i y w l v n l y s p m /	o a & a c w & m ? u e D u a c j i f u l e f ? y v i f y w l v n l o u w p m /	o a & a c w & m ? b & m ; B u d t e b ? a u s m u p m o l y l l f u s t ? y g V b m o m /

refq umv	y1 tu&myM (y1bmomtWu)	*y1 a' Oem* & Dt u&myM (ouwvbmomtWu)	tEd awmi y1 f tu&myM sm; (ygVbmomtWu)
at' 0 (6-7)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; axmi f t 1/2 t 1/2 yw/vn? y1pm/	&cl 1 a0omv h cw/! ouwvpm	oa&cw&m? ci l bulef? a&ayv m? ygVbmom/
at' 0 (7-8)		အကုသန္တ(ဒါရိယာရိသဒ္ဓါ)၍	ယသန္တ(ယကုပုပု)
	oa&acw&m? b&m; Bu 0 t 1/2 t 1/2 t 1/2? ab; yw/vn? y1pm/	&cl 1 a0omv h cw/! ouwvpm (a' Oem* & Dt u&m)	, clx 1 f E 11 fi (a&Sr h w 11 f) ' 11 & m 0 w h cw/! ygVbmom/ (r 1 f t u&m)
at' 0 (7-8)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; Bu 0 t 1/2 t 1/2? ab; yw/vn? y1pm/		
at' 0 (7-8)			
	oa&acw&m? b&m; Bu 0 t 1/2 t 1/2 t 1/2? ab; yw/vn? y1pm		a u s m u Bu 0 t 1/2 t 1/2, ? u 1 f t q y & 11? ygVbmom/
at' 0 (11)			
	(j r p o m; N r 11 a w 0) y k' h c w f a p m v t; r i f a u s m u p m? y 1 p m /	(j r p o m; N r 11 a w 0) y k' h c w f a p m v t; r i f a u s m u p m? o u w v p m (e m * & D t u & m)	(j r p o m; N r 11 a w 0) y k' h c w f a p m v t; r i f a u s m u p m? y g V b m o m /
at' 0 (11)			
	y k' N r 11 0 & y g w k g; r 1 w 1/2 k v p m a u s m b u y g a o m y 1 p m		
at' 0 (11)			
	y k' N r 11 a & q h w m 0 b & m; ? t k w f c l u h a u s m? y 1 p m		
at' 0 (12)			
	y k' N r 11 0 & m Z u k m & h a u s m u p m? y 1 p m /		y k' N r 11 0 & m Z u k m & f a u s m u p m? y g V b m o m /

rēf q umv	yī tu&myk (yībmomt w(ū))	*yā a' Oem* & D tu&myk (ouūwbmomt w(ū))	tēd awmiyī f tu&myk sm; (ygvbmomt w(ū))
at' 𐑀 (12)			 yk' 𐑀 a&f' 𐑀 u& b& m; ? ygvbmom/

azmfyyga&; xrl aumuEkwtsuf sm; t& ouūwbmom a&; xrl sm; ul at' (5)
 & mpDekusi fuyif & cīā' ou aOomvācwī ouūw urh' fpmrsm; 1/2 ygon/ *yā
 tu&mul to h' yk' 𐑀 at' (7) & mpk aemu yī f wōī a' Oem* & D tu& mzi h a&; om; cū
 ygon/ oa& acw& mwōī vn' xbuūw bmompum; a&; xrl 1/2 m a& mu 1/2 maom
 r& i f tu& m ta&; tom; jzpaom *yā tu& mzi f yī fa&; om; xm; ygon/

]]y&Z, (ouūw) wlyd; E(yī))
 #

y(2) ueDuācgi f uē fouūw-yī eā , pmaumuEkwtsuf

azmfyygywōī ouūwpmv wūl *yā tu& mzi h a&; om; lyō? yī pmv wūl yī tu& mzi h
 a&; om; xm; ygon/ urh' fpmv pckvn' fuyif bmompum; u f ym; onft avūuī tu& m
 toī vn' cī cm; to h' yk' xm; a lū mi f aw& ygon/

xlt wī ygvbmom a&; xrl wōī vn' ygvē s h yī tu& m? yī pmta&; tom; E s h
 toī f ym; rī ul aw& ygon/ cī bai 𐑀 k wōī f ygvā&; om; rī -

y(3) cī bai 𐑀 k wōī ygvpm (yvō tu& m)

[hōm tēd awmiyī f yvō tu& m? ta&; oō f yī f ul aw& ygon/ x h i 𐑀 k wōī f yī f
 yī pma&; xrl -

y(4) cī bai 𐑀 k wōī yī pm (yī tu& m)

[hōm yī tu& m? ta&; oō f yī f ul aw& ygon/ xlt yī f yī wā ygvpm a&; om; rī
 yī acwī umv pckvn' fuyif ygvbmomul tu& m trā r' jzi h a&; om; on/ yī tu& m
 ta&; pepū h vō to h' r' yk' y/

Z, m(10)ygVurhfpmt oftrsr#

p0f	urhfpmtrnf	tu&my#
1	oa&acw&m? ci lbulef? ai DuKv? ygVp/m/	
2	oa&acw&m? w0 fNy/rhlaygu? ygVp/m/	
3	oa&acw&m? b&m;Bu0 te0?ausnupmohy# f,ust? ygVp/m/	
4	oa&cw&m?ci lbulef? a&ayv#? ygVp/m/	
5	ausnubun#le, ? uef,qy&0? ygVp/m/	

azmfyyg aw0#ft& ysa'ow0f ygVpmtw0f y#tu&mpmta&;tom;ul ro#b
r#v#vuc#&m tEd awmif#f ta&;tu& wpr#str#ul to#y#l#umif azmfyE#f y#
onf

x#ub#om a&;om;r#p#f#ul y#acw#v#omru y#acw#v#umv jz#om
y#acw#v# t#y#i#&#bnf[kq#E#f ygonf/ p#on#ul j#r#p#om;#r#l# ayawmulefausni f, w#l#f
r#aw#om ou&mZi 441 x#? apm#v#r#i#facw#ausnupm (armi#armi#q# 2014? 2-13/
u ou#ox#v#ul #ygonf/

**y#(5) j#r#p#om;#r#l# ayawmulefausni f#w#l#f#aw#om ou&mZi441x#?
apm#v#r#i#facw#ausnupm**

rygaom yspmta&tom;uH tolykMualumi; aEhif;yt&ta&oGfyi pepful awU&yg on/ yspm ta&tom;qH &m orH; taxmuftxm;wp&ktjzplvnf; rSv; E;lygon/

yK&cwí r&? jrefm? ygVd -pmta&tom;rs;Esh yspm

yK&cwíonf yspmars&Ely&aemurS jyelvnawU&vm&aom tajctaejzpon/ xLumv yspmwf acwly&bmompum;wH vfr;hr;rs; ouDiVU&lygon/ xHumi h acwly&f r&? jrefmEsh ywH tu&? pmta&tom; qupyrbabmrsm;uH azmfj vlygon/

(1) r&?pmta&tom;Esh yK&cwí&h&usupm? tu&myH

at' (8) &mpDef;usi w&f , c&H;E;H;fi H e, hjrtw&f;½& avmb&D y&yxH a&S;H;la [mi; rsm;ü-a&S;re&usupm? ygV&usupmrsm;uH t&Ed awmiy&f to&f;rs; &, b&m;aom ta&tom;w;zi h a&om;xm;yg on/ a&S;e&bmomjzi h a&om;xm;aom re&usupm rsm;jzplygon/ t&Ed awmiy&f to&f;rs;uH &, h&om;xm;ly? xH&svpqifwufum yK&cwí r&?pmta&tom;rs; z&H;vm [e/lygon/ Z, m;(12)uHunlyg/

Z, m(12) a&S;re&?pmt u&myH

pOf	urH;pmtrnf	r&?qumv	urH;tu&myH
1	'&?mowD y&yxH re&usupm a&S;re&? u&?	at' (8) 0ef;usif	ဝဲဒါ ပြော အငါထံတွင်
2	'&?mowD y&yxH re&usupm a&S;re&? u&?	at' (8) 0ef;usif	အိမ်ထဲမှာ နံ့ပြန်မိတာ
3	'&?mowD y&yxH re&usupm a&S;re&? u&?	at' (8) 0ef;usif	ဝါးလှပျော့ပါးပါး
4	jrp&om;aywmulef? (apmv;ri;fvu&u) ausupm? re&?tu&?	at' (11)	
5	yK&H u&epp&om;ri;f twky&v&usupm re&?tu&?	at' (11)	
6	jynit& a&Iq&awmf b&m;re&usupm? re&?tu&? (yK&cwí)	at' (11)	
7	yK&H &MZur&f re&usupm? re&?tu&?	at' (12)	

t&Ed awmiy&f ta&tom;wH tajc&H ' &?mowD&cwí r&?pmta&tom;rs; z&H;vm [e/lygon/ xH&svpqifwufum yK&cwí r&?pmta&tom;rs; quvuz&H;vm [e/lygon/

(3) jrefmt u&myl tu&myl jcmemrlt ajctae

azmfyobnft wll f a&S0bjrefmt u&mojfyiul tu&myl sm; qubyrft & r&w&xlts & clbnf [baom tp0ft vmazmfyrbnf cl f r mvsul / ygon/ obomf yk jrefmES h acwlyl f umvwlf jrefmES h rwhbaom yltu&mojfyi f 1/2aeonful & mZurm&f ausmupmu oubaoxlvul / ygon/

Z, m(14) jrefmpmt u&myl h yspmt u&myl jcmemrl

1	yk&myl & mZurm&f ausmupm? yltu&myl	at' (12)	
2	yk&myl & mZurm&f ausmupm? ygl/bmomt u&myl	at' (12)	
3	yk&myl & mZurm&f ausmupm? r&ft u&myl	at' (12)	
4	yk&myl & mZurm&f ausmupm? jrefmt u&myl	at' (12)	

azmfyygZ, m; t& r&? ygVl jrefmwll pmta& tom; to f r n wpr&wnf [k rsvf, Ell f avmu&tmi f whaeonful aw&ygon/ ysrn qubyr&avmu&tmi f to f u&e onful jri&w&ae&ygon/ x&llumi h yk&w&lf y&w&w&aeon/ jrefmES h rwhbaom o&jcm; jzpa&eonh y&pum; u& ajymq&cl elwlygon/ y&pmu&lvnf a& c&lu [elwlygon/ x&ll w&lf yk&w&lf x&d y&w&bnf jrefm&jrrn v&r&pkvp&ct jzpf & y&w&n&clbnf [k , lqrd ygon/

jcll b&oytsuf

(1) y&spmta& tom; u& at' (2) & mp&cl&w&lf a&st&ed ajrmu&lyl f? awmi&lyl f jAm [p tu&myl ta& to f u& f sm; ubl jAm [tu&myl ta& to f u& w&pk&ct jzpf y&w&w&, cl&cl f ES h y&w&lonf t&q&an&fo&llom wufus&ll b&mom&pum wpr&cl u& ajymq&lyl? jrefm&jray:rs jrefmwll rwh&cl&baom v&om; r&st&EG pkvp&ct jzpf azmfy Ell ygon/

(2) y&w&lonf pmta& tom; tww&u&ll a&st&ed om; w&xlts & 1/2&lyl? r&ll b&mom pum; tw&lf jylyi&zelw&? w&xlts r&sm; jzi h a& om; c&lu onf at' (3-4) & mp&cl&w&lf pwif z&ll&vmonf at' (4-7) & mp&cl&w&lf w&lf us, p&n to f j&yl&aeonful aw&ygon/ at' (7-9) & mp&cl&w&lf acwlyl f b&mom&pum; r&sm; \ v&r&ll r&llumi h ta& to f ajymi f vl v&myl&baemu? at' (9-11) & mp&cl&w&lf y&spmta& tom; aw&w&ri taxmuft xm; enf yg; i? tmenf v&maom pmta& tom; t&jzpf r&svf, Ell ygon/

(3)at' (11-12)&mpLum;w0f yk'k'cwlydpm aw&jci;fallumi h xllumvtxdydvrd;
 wW&eNy0? ydpm;? ydpmu'vnt; olaeao;allumi f r&f;qEli ygon/ jrefmtrnrcbl
 objcm;vrdp'kwpc'ktjzpf ½&Eli elwygon/ jrefmw'bn'vnt; ydpm? ydtu&m½&e
 onhw'if ydtu&m? ydpm'ta&;pep'ull jrefmtu&m? jrefmp'm'ta&;pep'oll rajymi;f'cl
 r&ftu&m? r&ep'm'ta&;pep'ulbm jrefmtu&m? jrefmp'm'ta&;pep'oll ajymi;f'v'clLumi f
 aw'ljric&lygon/

edH

azmfyygtallumi f rsm'nf ydpm ydtu&m'w'ull tajcjy'ki uEly'v'v'm'cl'om ola'woe
 rsm;u'li p'pn'f;um'wi'f'x'm;jci'f;jzplygon/ av'lv'm'r'k'v'p'c'k'v'ull azmfy&on'ft'w'ul
 em;v'n'r'c'ub'c'j'ci'f' paom t'cu'ft'c'r'sm; ½&v'm'Ellygon/ x'lt'w'ul v'm'a&mu'fa'q'Ga'Es'j'ci'f'
 ar;j're'f'j'ci'f'r'sm; j'y'Ellygon/ aumi'fa'om t'bu'j'y'k'r'sm;u'lv'nt; v'uc'li bu'k'p'm; o'br;
 ygrn/ qu'lv'ul ydpmay? yd'bm'ompum;? yd'ta&;tom;r'sm;E's'h r&ep'may? r&e'lb'om
 pum; r&e'ft'a&;tom;r'sm;u'li oi'num;a&;tax'mu'ft'ujz'p'&e'f bu'k'y'r'fa'q'mi &u'lo'br;rn'f
 jzplygon/

ur'f'ul'p'm&i'f

pl'bm'a't'mi' 00/ (1974)/ **at' 'Bjcmu&mpESh i'f'rw'if'&cl'fynb'ltu&m'** &e'ule'! Or'f'a't'mi' p'may/
 azarmi'k'wi' 00/ (1958)/ **bmomavmu'ur'f'** &e'ule'p'm? ay'Ar'm'e'y'El'y'w'ul/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' 00/ (2006)/ **y'dp'm'ta&;tom'r'sm'r's An'f, 0b& (t'p' t')to'W** jyn'lv'u'ib'w'f
 j're'f'm'p'm'x'm'e'w'0'f'z'w'ul'm;a'om ola'woe'p'm'w'r'f'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' armi'v' (2006)/ **j're'f'm'El'li'k'j'ur'ih'f'p'm'r's' y'dtu&mo'P'h'e'r'sm'ES'h y'dp'm'v'W
 a&;omy'p'ep'f'm'av'lv'm'c'sul** 2006-yg&*l'bu's'r'f? &e'ule'lv'u'ib'w'f/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' a'gu'lv'm/ 2009/ **]]y'dp'm'umi'f'tajc'f'p'm'v'li, f'm'av'lv'm'r'f'** Journal of Myanmar
 Academy of Arts and Science. Vol.No.7-B, pm53-67/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' 2009/ **y'dp'm'umi'f'tajc'f'p'm'v'li, f'm'av'lv'm'c'sul** &e'ule'! j're'f'm'El'li' H O'z'AE's'io'y'li
 t'z'bo'lv'iw'ib'ol'fa'om ola'woe'p'm'w'r'f'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' a'gu'lv'm/ (2010)/ **u'el'q'f'f'g'v'au's'up'm'r'a&Stu&mo'lj'y'if'sm av'lv'm c'sul**
 jyn'lv'W jyn'lv'u'ib'w'ol'w'ib'ol'fa'om ola'woe'p'm'w'r'f'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' (2010)/ **y'dp'm'ta&;tom'r'sm'r'sAn'f, 0b& (t'p' t') to'W** &e'ule'! j're'f'm'El'li' H O'z'AE's' h
 o'y'li' t'z'bo'lv'iw'ib'ol'fa'om ola'woe'p'm'w'r'f'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' (2012)/ **y'dp'm'ta&;o'lj'y'if's'p'ub'au'lv'to'lr'sm/** &e'ule'! j're'f'm'El'li' H O'z'AE's' h o'y'li
 t'z'bo'lv'iw'ib'ol'fa'om ola'woe'p'm'w'r'f'/

armi'f'armi'f'a'q' a'gu'lv'm/ (2014)/ **j'r'p'om'li'hy'aw'm'aus'ni'f? au's'up'm'aw'm'ib'uf r'su'El'f?
 tu&my'lt'm'av'lv'm'c'sul** a&Sa[mi'f'ola'woe'ES'h tr'cl'om;jy'w'ul'0'p'0' Xme/ p'm'w'r'f'z'w'y'f's
 ola'woe'p'm'w'r'f'/

om'j'r'w'f' 00 (o'ly'f'f') (1963)/ **y'z'w'p'm'** &e'ule'! ti'lv'm'ae'&S'e, v'

	BC-1	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
Northern Indian Scripts	AD-2	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
	AD-4	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
	AD-7	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
Southern Indian Scripts	AD-3	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
	AD-4	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
	AD-6	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜
Pyu Script	AD-3	𑀓		𑀕		𑀗		𑀙		𑀛	
	AD-5	𑀓		𑀕		𑀗		𑀙		𑀛	
	AD-12	𑀓		𑀕		𑀗		𑀙		𑀛	
Mon Script	AD-12	𑀓	𑀔	𑀕	𑀖	𑀗	𑀘	𑀙	𑀚	𑀛	𑀜

PL Gupta Acient & Medieval Indian Alphabets Tables; yk yif, ? tif0? jrefm
 aumuxifitu&myrsm? 1979? aemuquwZ, m;rsn;/ IG-Guhler, 1904, Indian
 Palaeography; D. Dinger, 1949, The Alphabets; B. Pandey, 1957, Indian Palaeography;
 ODomjrw? 1963? yszwpm/ ODr? 1961? jrefmtu&njzphay:vmyW ODomjrw? 1956?
 reJrefmtu&morif/ ODrkmatmi? 1974? 6- &mpES h ifrwi r&cifjynbH tu&m
 rsn;ES 1975? tmeEp'E&p&mp&cif aOomvDrif? a':oefaq 1992? yspmcilba&ayvH
 avlvmsu/ ysurHfpmrsm;/ wWzDpmvHrsm;uHnEifjy/pxm;onf